

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of substituted 3-(phthalazine-1-ylamino)alkanoic acid containing imidoxy moiety

Vijay Kumar Salvi, Gangotri Pemawat, Archita Bapna and G. L. Talesara*

Synthetic Organic Chemistry Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 001, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : gtalesara@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 12 May 2008, revised 16 January 2009, accepted 20 January 2009

Abstract : Hydrozinolysis of phthalyl derivatives of amino acid 1a-c afforded [(4-oxo-3,4-dihydrophthalazine-1-yl)amino]substituted acetic acid 2a-c, which on reaction with $\text{POCl}_3/\text{PCl}_5$ gave [(4-chlorophthalazine-1-yl)amino]substituted acetic acid 3a-c. This when condensed with *N*-hydroxyphthalimide/*N*-hydroxysuccinimide 4a-b yielded phthalimido or succinimido-2-((4-phthalazine-1-yl)amino)substituted acetic acid 5a-f. Condensation of compounds 2a-c with ω -bromoalkoxyphthalimide 6a-b furnished the corresponding 2-[(3-{2-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2*H*-isoindol-2-yl)oxy]ethyl}-4-oxo-3,4-dihydrophthalazine-1-yl)amino]substituted acetic acid 7a-f. All the compounds were screened for antimicrobial activities.

Keywords : Phthalazine, ω -bromoalkoxyphthalimide, condensation, antimicrobial activity, *N*-hydroxyphthalimide.

Introduction

Pyridazine derivatives received considerable interest due to vast number of research papers and patents dealing with their synthesis^{1,2}, chemistry^{3,4} and biological activities⁵. Some of the phthalazine derivatives are commonly used as therapeutic agents⁶, ligands in transition metal catalysis⁷, chemiluminescent materials⁸, optical applications and clinical medicine^{9,10}. Pyridazinones reduce blood pressure¹¹, inhibit platelet aggregation¹², exhibit positive inotropic¹³ and phosphodiesterase¹⁴ activity. The presence of D-amino acid residues in antibiotics such as tryocidine¹⁵, penicillin and aerosporin¹⁶ has aroused interest in the inhibitory potentialities of various nitrogen heterocycles containing amino acids.

A large number of imidoxy derivatives of various heterocycles reported to demonstrate a wide range of pharmacological activities like antimalarial¹⁷, anticonvulsant¹⁸, anticancer¹⁹ etc. Several derivatives of this framework have been synthesized^{20,21} by us. In view of the above-mentioned facts, it is felt expedient to synthesize phthalamido/succinimido 2-((4-phthalazine-1-yl)amino)-substituted acetic acid 5a-f and 2-[(3-{2-[(1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2*H*-isoindol-2-yl)oxy]ethyl}-4-oxo-3,4-dihydrophthalazine-1-yl)amino]substituted acetic acid 7a-f.

Results and discussion

In the present investigation, hydrozinolysis of phthalyl

derivatives of amino acid 1a-c in boiling *n*-butanol furnished [(4-oxo-3,4-dihydrophthalazine-1-yl)amino]-substituted acetic acid 2a-c. The structure was supported by spectral data and elemental analysis. It showed NH group frequency at 3210-3390 cm^{-1} and ¹H NMR signals at δ 8.5 (1H, s, NH), 9.98 for COOH (1H, s, COOH). These compounds when reacted with $\text{POCl}_3/\text{PCl}_5$ in ethanol yielded [(4-chlorophthalazine-1-yl)amino]substituted acetic acid 3a-c. Structure of these were confirmed on the basis of IR spectral peaks appearing at 757 cm^{-1} indicating presence of C-Cl stretching, the PMR spectrum displayed a sharp singlet at δ 10.24-10.12 (1H, COOH), a singlet at δ 6.89-6.80 (1H, NH) and mass spectral peak in favor of the structure of synthesized compounds. Compounds 3a-c when condensed with *N*-hydroxyphthalimide/*N*-hydroxysuccinimide 4a-b in DMF/TEA yielded corresponding disubstituted phthalazine derivatives 5a-f. Structural proof of 5a-f rest on spectral studies of the IR spectra viz. disappearance of C-Cl peak between 768-757 cm^{-1} and appearance of new N-O stretching at 1390 cm^{-1} clearly indicate the presence of imidoxy group. Molecular ion peak $[\text{M}]^{+*}$ and *m/z* values (fragmentation) observed at 162 and 114 show the presence of phthalimido/succinimido moiety respectively in synthesized compounds. Condensation of compounds 2a-c with ω -bromoalkoxyphthalimide 6a-b in a bifurcated route using pyridine as base in absolute alco-

hol media gave corresponding disubstituted phthalazine derivatives 7a-f. IR band due to NO group appearing near 924 cm^{-1} indicates that NH group of phthalazine has been replaced by imidoxy moiety. Nonparticipation of NH group of 4-substituted amino acid in phthalazinone in which reaction with electrophile due to existence as zwitterion was confirmed by IR spectra.

Antibacterial activity :

Twelve compounds have been screened for antibacte-

rial activity. Three Gram-negative *P. mirabilis* (org 1), *K. pneumoniae* (org 2), *S. typhi* (org 4) and one Gram-positive *B. subtilis* (org 3) bacterial strains were used for antibacterial screening. *Ciprofloxacin* was used as standard drug. For the present investigations, only cup or well method was used. Nutrient Agar-Agar media was sterilized by autoclaving at 15 psi and $121\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 min. The medium was poured in Petri dishes and left to solidify. These were incubated with 0.2 ml suspension of organism by spread plate method. Three or four wells of

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physical and analytical data for synthesized compounds 2a-c, 3a-c, 5a-f and 7a-f

Compd.	Mol. formula	Mol. wt.	R	n	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Found (Calcd.) % N
2a	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	219	H	-	85	210	19.14 (19.17)
2b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃	233	CH ₃	-	80	288	17.99 (18.02)
2c	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃	295	C ₆ H ₅	-	80	310	14.20 (14.23)
3a	C ₁₀ H ₈ ClN ₃ O ₂	237	H	-	70	260	17.64 (17.68)
3b	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂	251	CH ₃	-	75	290	16.68 (16.70)
3c	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ O ₂	313	C ₆ H ₅	-	65	320	13.35 (13.39)
5a	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₅	364	H	-	70	280	15.35 (15.38)
5b	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₅	378	CH ₃	-	65	305	14.79 (14.81)
5c	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅	440	C ₆ H ₅	-	75	270	12.69 (12.72)
5d	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₅	316	H	-	60	250	17.68 (17.71)
5e	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₅	330	CH ₃	-	60	225	16.94 (16.96)
5f	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅	392	C ₆ H ₅	-	55	260	14.26 (14.28)
7a	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆	408	H	2	60	240	13.68 (13.72)
7b	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆	422	CH ₃	2	65	280	13.22 (13.26)
7c	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆	484	C ₆ H ₅	2	70	305	11.53 (11.56)
7d	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₆	436	H	4	65	265	12.81 (12.84)
7e	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₆	450	CH ₃	4	55	270	12.41 (12.44)
7f	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₆	512	C ₆ H ₅	4	60	308	10.90 (10.93)

11 mm diameter were made in the medium with the help of a sterile borer and filled with 500 ppm solution of testing compounds in DMF. Other wells for standard drugs were also filled with standard concentrations. These Petri dishes were incubated at 37 °C, the Petri dishes were examined for zone of inhibition after 24–48 h.

Data in Table 3 reveals that antibacterial activity of the synthesized compounds is weak to moderate against all the bacterial strains. Activity decreases in the order org 1 > org 2 > org 3 > org 4. Compound 5b has got good activity against first three organisms. While compound 7b shows a poor activity against all the four organisms. Over all activity of synthesized compounds is less in comparison to standard drugs.

Antifungal activity :

Two pathogenic fungi have been used for antifungal activity namely *C. albicans* and *A. fumigatus*. *Fluconazole* was used as standard drug. These were sub cultured and characterized by standard methods. Growth medium used was Sabouraud agar. Cup or well method was used here also for screening of the compounds. Decreasing growth of fungi with increasing concentration of compounds has been manifested by MIC studies and this value was noticed above 500 ppm. Abundant was observed in com-

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of compounds 5a-f and 7a-f

Compd.	Antibacterial activity (500 ppm)			
	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>
5a	7 (0.50)	-	6 (0.41)	2 (0.18)
5b	9 (0.64)	6 (0.50)	7 (0.53)	2 (0.18)
5c	-	5 (0.41)	7 (0.53)	3 (0.27)
5d	4 (0.29)	5 (0.41)	5 (0.38)	4 (0.36)
5e	2 (0.14)	7 (0.58)	6 (0.46)	3 (0.27)
5f	5 (0.35)	4 (0.33)	4 (0.30)	3 (0.27)
7a	5 (0.35)	6 (0.50)	5 (0.38)	4 (0.36)
7b	-	3 (0.25)	2 (0.15)	2 (0.18)
7c	4 (0.28)	-	5 (0.38)	2 (0.18)
7d	4 (0.28)	5 (0.41)	6 (0.41)	3 (0.27)
7e	3 (0.21)	6 (0.50)	5 (0.38)	2 (0.18)
7f	7 (0.50)	4 (0.33)	-	4 (0.36)
Standard	14	12	13	11

Zone of inhibition in mm (activity index).

Activity index = Inhibition zone of the compound/Inhibition zone of standard.

pound free (control) medium. DMF was used as solvent. Significant antifungal activity was observed against both fungal strains. Results show that synthesized compounds exhibited better activity as compared to standard. All the

Table 3. Antifungal activity of compounds 5a-f and 7a-f

Compd.	Antifungal activity (500 ppm)	
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>
5a	10 (1.42)	11 (1.37)
5b	-	12 (1.50)
5c	11 (1.57)	10 (1.25)
5d	13 (1.85)	12 (1.50)
5e	14 (2.00)	13 (1.62)
5f	12 (1.71)	10 (1.25)
7a	11 (1.57)	10 (1.25)
7b	10 (1.42)	12 (1.50)
7c	11 (1.57)	-
7d	13 (1.85)	10 (1.25)
7e	11 (1.57)	12 (1.50)
7f	12 (1.71)	13 (1.62)
Standard	7	8

Zone of inhibition in mm (activity index).
Activity index = Inhibition zone of the compound/Inhibition zone of standard.

compounds show very good activity. Compounds 5e and 7f show very high activity index as compare to standard. Compounds 5b and 7c show negligible activity. Activity index of all other compounds is between 1.25–2.00 which is given in Table 3.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. ^1H NMR spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on Bruker WM-400 (400 MHz FT NMR) spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra (KBr disc) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1800 and Shimadzu 8201 PC (4000–350 cm^{-1}) FTIR spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were determined on Jeol D-300 (EI) and Jeol SX-102 (FAB) spectrometer. Purity of the synthesized compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel-G plates using *n*-hexane and benzene as eluent. Compounds 1a-c²² and 6a-b²³ were prepared according to literature procedures.

Synthesis of [(4-oxo-3,4-dihydrophthalazine-1-yl)amino]acetic acid (2a) :

A mixture of phthalyl derivatives of amino acid 1a (0.05 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 mol) in 40 ml *n*-butanol was refluxed for 4 h. The excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure and resultant solid was separated, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

IR (KBr) : 3307 (N-H str.), 3120 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1703, 1690 (C=O str.), 1633 cm^{-1} (C=N str.); ^1H NMR

(CDCl_3) : δ 9.98 (1H, s, COOH), 8.25 (1H, br s, NH), 7.54–7.18 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.91 (1H, s, NH-CH₂), 4.22 (2H, s, CH₂); MS : m/z 219 [M]⁺, 175 [M-CO₂]⁺, 145 [C₈H₅N₂O]⁺, 104 [C₇H₄O]⁺, 100 [C₃H₄N₂O₂]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 74 [C₂H₄NO₂]⁺, 65 [C₅H₅]⁺.

Compounds 2b-c have also been synthesized by similar method. Characteristic spectral data of these compounds are given below :

(2b) : IR (KBr) : 3220 (N-H str.), 3110 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1695–1692 (C=O str.), 1625 cm^{-1} (C=N str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 10.02 (1H, s, COOH), 8.32 (1H, br s, NH), 7.65–7.22 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.89 (1H, s, NH-CH₂), 4.12 (1H, q, CH), 2.43 (3H, d, CH₃); MS : m/z 233 [M]⁺, 189 [M-CO₂]⁺, 145 [C₈H₅N₂O]⁺, 114 [C₄H₆N₂O₂]⁺, 104 [C₇H₄O]⁺, 88 [C₃H₆NO₂]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 65 [C₅H₅]⁺.

(2c) : IR (KBr) : 3228 (N-H str.), 3080 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1698–1694 (C=O str.), 1618 cm^{-1} (C=N str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 10.04 (1H, s, COOH), 8.31 (1H, br s, NH), 7.64–7.36 (9H, m, Ar-H), 6.93 (1H, s, NH-CH₂), 4.44 (1H, s, -CH); MS : m/z 295 [M]⁺, 251 [M-CO₂]⁺, 176 [C₉H₈N₂O₂]⁺, 150 [C₈H₆NO₂]⁺, 145 [C₈H₅N₂O]⁺, 104 [C₇H₄C]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 65 [C₅H₅]⁺.

Synthesis of [(4-chlorophthalazine-1-yl)amino]acetic acid (3a) :

To a suspension of 2a (0.01 mol) in ethanol, PCl₅ (0.01 mol) or POCl₃ (5 mL) were added. The reaction mixture was heated for 4 h on steam bath. Reaction mixture was cooled and then poured slowly into ice cold dil. HCl with constant stirring. The separated solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from methanol.

IR (KBr) : 3321 (N-H str.), 3021 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1710 (C=O str.), 1635 (C=N str.), 757 cm^{-1} (C-Cl str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 10.15 (1H, s, COOH), 6.89 (1H, s, NH), 7.72–7.31 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.31 (2H, s, CH₂); MS : m/z 239 [M+2]⁺, 237 [M]⁺, 193 [M-CO₂]⁺, 163 [C₈H₄N₂Cl]⁺, 100 [C₃H₄N₂O₂]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 74 [C₂H₄NO₂]⁺, 65 [C₅H₅]⁺.

Compounds 3b-c were prepared by similar method with minor change in reaction conditions. Their spectral data are given below :

(3b) : IR (KBr) : 3225 (N-H str.), 3090 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1715 (C=O str.), 1628 (C=N str.), 762 cm^{-1} (C-Cl str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 10.22 (1H, s, COOH), 6.80 (1H, s, NH), 7.62–7.31 (4H, m, Ar-H), 4.25 (1H, m, CH), 2.68 (3H, d, CH₃); MS : m/z 253 [M+2]⁺,

251 [M]⁺, 207 [M-CO₂]⁺, 163 [C₈H₄N₂Cl]⁺, 100 [C₃H₄N₂O₂]⁺, 88 [C₃H₆NO₂]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 65 [C₅H₅]⁺.

(3c) : IR (KBr) : 3328 (N-H str.), 3185 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1720 (C=O str.), 1640 (C=N str.), 768 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 10.23 (1H, s, COOH), 6.85 (1H, s, NH), 7.72-7.41 (8H, m, Ar-H), 4.62 (1H, s, CH); MS : *m/z* 315 [M+2]⁺, 313 [M]⁺, 269 [M-CO₂]⁺, 163 [C₈H₄N₂Cl]⁺, 100 [C₃H₄N₂O₂]⁺, 77 [C₆H₅]⁺, 65 [C₅H₅]⁺.

Synthesis of succinimido 2-((4-phthalazine-1-yl)amino)acetic acid (5a) :

To a solution of compound 3a (0.01 mol) in dry DMF (25 mL), *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (1.63 g, 0.01 mol) and TEA (0.01 mol) were added. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and refluxed for 5 h, and then it was cooled. The precipitate of triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off. The filtrate was slowly poured into ice (50 g) with constant stirring. The solid obtained was recrystallized from ethanol.

IR (KBr) : 3257 (N-H str.), 3150-3020 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1705 (C=O str.), 1640 (C=N str.), 206 (C-N str.), 935 cm⁻¹ (N-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 9.92 (1H, s, COOH), 7.66-7.09 (8H, m, Ar-H), 6.54 (1H, s, NH), 4.31 (2H, s, CH₂); MS : *m/z* 364 [M]⁺, 363 [M-H]⁺, 320 [M-CO₂]⁺, 312 [M-C₄H₄]⁺, 290 [M-C₂H₅NO₂]⁺, 288 [M-C₆H₄]⁺, 264 [M-C₃H₄N₂O₂]⁺, 188 [C₉H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 176 [M-C₉H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 162 [C₈H₄NO₃]⁺, 132 [C₈H₄O₂]⁺, 128 [C₈H₄N₂]⁺, 104 [C₇H₄O]⁺, 100 [C₃H₄N₂O₂]⁺.

Compounds 5b-f have been prepared by the similar process with minor modifications, using *N*-hydroxysuccinimide and *N*-hydroxyphthalimide alternatively. Their spectral data are given below :

(5b) : IR (KBr) : 3310 (N-H str.), 3125-3010 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1710 (C=O str.), 1635 (C=N str.), 1212 (C-N str.), 932 cm⁻¹ (N-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 10.03 (1H, s, COOH), 7.68-7.04 (8H, m, Ar-H), 6.52 (1H, s, NH), 4.42 (1H, m, CH), 2.51 (3H, d, CH₃); MS : *m/z* 378 [M]⁺, 377 [M-H]⁺, 334 [M-CO₂]⁺, 326 [M-C₄H₄]⁺, 290 [M-C₃H₆NO₂]⁺, 302 [M-C₆H₄]⁺, 264 [M-C₄H₆N₂O₂]⁺, 188 [C₉H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 190 [M-C₉H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 162 [C₈H₄NO₃]⁺, 132 [C₈H₄O₂]⁺, 128 [C₈H₄N₂]⁺, 104 [C₇H₄O]⁺, 100 [C₃H₄N₂O₂]⁺.

(5c) : IR (KBr) : 3235 (N-H str.), 3160-3030 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1720 (C=O str.), 1620 (C=N str.), 1205 (C-N str.), 929 cm⁻¹ (N-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 10.11 (1H, s, COOH), 7.62-7.13 (12H, m, Ar-H), 6.56

(1H, s, NH), 4.51 (1H, s, CH); MS : *m/z* 440 [M]⁺, 439 [M-H]⁺, 396 [M-CO₂]⁺, 388 [M-C₄H₄]⁺, 364 [M-C₆H₄]⁺, 290 [M-C₆H₈NO₂]⁺, 264 [M-C₉H₈N₂O₂]⁺, 252 [M-C₉H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 188 [C₉H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 132 [C₈H₄O₂]⁺, 128 [C₈H₄N₂]⁺, 104 [C₇H₄O]⁺.

(5d) : IR (KBr) : 3325 (N-H str.), 3170-3000 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1714 (C=O str.), 1594 (C=N str.), 1210 (C-N str.), 930 cm⁻¹ (N-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 10.06 (1H, s, COOH), 8.61 (1H, s, NH), 7.81-7.59 (8H, m, Ar-H), 4.55 (2H, s, CH₂), 3.82 (2H, t, CH₂-O), 2.96 (2H, t, CH₂-N), 2.51 (2H, m, CH₂CH₂O), 2.23 (2H, m, CH₂, CH₂N); MS : *m/z* 316 [M]⁺, 315 [M-H]⁺, 272 [M-CO₂]⁺, 264 [M-C₂H₄]⁺, 240 [M-C₆H₄]⁺, 242 [M-C₂H₄NO₂]⁺, 200 [M-C₃H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 116 [M-C₃H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 132 [C₈H₄O₂]⁺, 128 [C₈H₄N₂]⁺, 114 [C₄H₄NO₃]⁺, 100 [C₃H₄N₂O₂]⁺, 84 [C₄H₄O₂]⁺, 56 [C₃H₄O]⁺.

(5e) : IR (KBr) : 3250 (N-H str.), 3100-3010 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1708 (C=O str.), 1590 (C=N str.), 1225 (C-N str.), 938 cm⁻¹ (N-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 9.94 (1H, s, COOH), 7.63-7.18 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.61 (1H, s, NH), 4.48 (1H, m, CH), 2.42 (3H, d, CH₃), 2.75 (4H, s, CH₂-CH₂); MS : *m/z* 330 [M]⁺, 329 [M-H]⁺, 286 [M-CO₂]⁺, 278 [M-C₂H₄]⁺, 254 [M-C₆H₄]⁺, 230 [M-C₄H₆NO₂]⁺, 214 [M-C₃H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 116 [M-C₃H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 128 [C₈H₄N₂]⁺, 114 [C₄H₄NO₃]⁺, 100 [C₃H₄N₂O₂]⁺, 84 [C₄H₄O₂]⁺, 56 [C₃H₄O]⁺.

(5f) : IR (KBr) : 3315 (N-H str.), 3170-3010 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1716 (C=O str.), 1610 (C=N str.), 1220 (C-N str.), 936 cm⁻¹ (N-O str.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 10.25 (1H, s, COOH), 7.672-7.20 (8H, m, Ar-H), 6.55 (1H, s, NH), 4.61 (1H, s, CH), 2.80 (4H, s, CH₂-CH₂); MS : *m/z* 392 [M]⁺, 391 [M-H]⁺, 348 [M-CO₂]⁺, 340 [M-C₂H₄]⁺, 316 [M-C₆H₄]⁺, 242 [M-C₈H₈NO₂]⁺, 276 [M-C₃H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 116 [M-C₃H₄N₂O₃]⁺, 128 [C₈H₄N₂]⁺, 114 [C₄H₄NO₃]⁺, 84 [C₄H₄O₂]⁺, 56 [C₃H₄O]⁺.

Synthesis of 2-[(3-{2-[1,3-dioxo-1,3-dihydro-2H-isoindol-2-yl]oxy}ethyl)-4-oxo-3,4-dihydrophthalazine-1-yl]amino]acetic acid (7a) :

Compound 2a (0.01 mol) and ω-bromoalkoxyphthalimide (0.01 mol) were dissolved in 30 mL ethanol and then pyridine (2 mL) was added to it as a base. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 h. Excess of solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. Resulting solid was cooled, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

IR (KBr) : 3340 (N-H str.), 3125 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1720 (C=O str.), 1620 (C=N str.), 1244 (C-N str.),

925 cm^{-1} (N-O str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 10.01 (1H, s, COOH), 8.51 (1H, s, NH), 7.97–7.83 (8H, m, Ar-H), 4.23 (2H, s, CH_2), 3.82 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 2.79 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-N}$); MS: m/z 408 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$, 380 $[\text{M-CO}]^{+\bullet}$, 364 $[\text{M-CO}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 332 $[\text{M-C}_6\text{H}_5]^{+\bullet}$, 308 $[\text{M-C}_3\text{H}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 232 $[\text{M-C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 190 $[\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 176 $[\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 162 $[\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 132 $[\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 128 $[\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{N}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 104 $[\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}]^{+\bullet}$, 100 $[\text{C}_3\text{H}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$.

Compounds 7b–f have been prepared by similar process with minor modifications, using ω -bromoethoxyphthalimide and ω -bromobutoxyphthalimide alternatively. Their spectral data are given below:

(7b): IR (KBr): 3350 (N-H str.), 3110 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1718 (C=O str.), 1618 (C=N str.), 1235 (C-N str.), 926 cm^{-1} (N-O str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 10.10 (1H, s, COOH), 8.54 (1H, s, NH), 7.95–7.75 (8H, m, Ar-H), 4.21 (1H, m, CH), 3.84 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 2.91 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-N}$), 2.62 (3H, d, CH_3); MS: m/z 422 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$, 394 $[\text{M-CO}]^{+\bullet}$, 378 $[\text{M-CO}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 346 $[\text{M-C}_6\text{H}_5]^{+\bullet}$, 308 $[\text{M-C}_3\text{H}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 246 $[\text{M-C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 190 $[\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 176 $[\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 162 $[\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 104 $[\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}]^{+\bullet}$.

(7c): IR (KBr): 3345 (N-H str.), 3050 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1712 (C=O str.), 1598 (C=N str.), 1224 (C-N str.), 919 cm^{-1} (N-O str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 10.08 (1H, s, COOH), 8.49 (1H, s, NH), 7.83–7.57 (12H, m, Ar-H), 4.29 (1H, s, CH), 3.79 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 2.93 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-N}$); MS: m/z 484 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$, 456 $[\text{M-CO}]^{+\bullet}$, 440 $[\text{M-CO}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 408 $[\text{M-C}_6\text{H}_4]^{+\bullet}$, 308 $[\text{M-C}_3\text{H}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 190 $[\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 176 $[\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 162 $[\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 104 $[\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}]^{+\bullet}$.

(7d): IR (KBr): 3365 (N-H str.), 3068 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1710 (C=O str.), 1630 (C=N str.), 1215 (C-N str.), 931 cm^{-1} (N-O str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 10.06 (1H, s, COOH), 8.61 (1H, s, NH), 7.81–7.59 (8H, m, Ar-H), 4.55 (2H, s, CH_2), 3.82 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 2.96 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-N}$), 2.51 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}$), 2.23 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$); MS: m/z 436 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$, 408 $[\text{M-CO}]^{+\bullet}$, 392 $[\text{M-CO}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 360 $[\text{M-C}_6\text{H}_4]^{+\bullet}$, 336 $[\text{M-C}_3\text{H}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 260 $[\text{M-C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 218 $[\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 190 $[\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 176 $[\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 162 $[\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 104 $[\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}]^{+\bullet}$.

(7e): IR (KBr): 3370 (N-H str.), 3080 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1715 (C=O str.), 1595 (C=N str.), 1209 (C-N str.), 929 cm^{-1} (N-O str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 10.07 (1H, s, COOH), 8.56 (1H, s, NH), 7.81–7.61 (8H, m, Ar-H), 4.51 (1H, m, CH), 3.89 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 2.98 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-N}$), 2.62 (3H, d, CH_3), 2.48 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}$), 2.27 (2H, m, CH_2 , CH_2N); MS: m/z 450 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$, 422 $[\text{M-CO}]^{+\bullet}$, 406 $[\text{M-CO}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 398 $[\text{M-C}_4\text{H}_4]^{+\bullet}$,

374 $[\text{M-C}_6\text{H}_4]^{+\bullet}$, 336 $[\text{M-C}_4\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 274 $[\text{M-C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 218 $[\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 190 $[\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 176 $[\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 162 $[\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 132 $[\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 104 $[\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}]^{+\bullet}$.

(7f): IR (KBr): 3355 (N-H str.), 3125 (C-H str., Ar-H), 1720 (C=O str.), 1622 (C=N str.), 1218 (C-N str.), 934 cm^{-1} (N-O str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3): δ 10.12 (1H, s, COOH), 8.61 (1H, s, NH), 7.80–7.66 (8H, m, Ar-H), 4.58 (1H, s, CH), 3.92 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 2.90 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-N}$), 2.52 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}$), 2.25 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$); MS: m/z 512 $[\text{M}]^{+\bullet}$, 484 $[\text{M-CO}]^{+\bullet}$, 468 $[\text{M-CO}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 460 $[\text{M-C}_4\text{H}_4]^{+\bullet}$, 436 $[\text{M-C}_6\text{H}_4]^{+\bullet}$, 336 $[\text{M-C}_9\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 190 $[\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 176 $[\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 162 $[\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{NO}_3]^{+\bullet}$, 132 $[\text{C}_8\text{H}_4\text{O}_2]^{+\bullet}$, 104 $[\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}]^{+\bullet}$.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur, for providing laboratory facilities and to the Director, RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow, India for providing spectral and analytical data. Authors are grateful to Antimicrobial Research Laboratory, particularly Dr. Kanika Sharma, Department of Botany, M. L. Sukhadia University for evaluating antimicrobial activity. Two of the authors (Vijay Kumar Salvi and Archita Bapna) are thankful to CSIR, New Delhi for providing necessary financial assistance.

References

- C. J. McIntyre, G. S. Ponticello, N. J. Liverton, S. J. Okeefe, E. A. Oneill, M. Pang, C. D. Schwartz and D. A. Claremon, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2002, 12, 689.
- R. R. Nagawade, V. V. Khanna, S. S. Bhagwat and D. B. Shinde, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2005, 40, 1325.
- E. Sotelo and E. Ravina, *Synth. Commun.*, 2002, 32, 1675.
- M. P. Giovannoni, V. Dal Piaz, B. M. Kwon, M. K. Kim, Y. K. Kim, L. Toma, D. Barlocco, F. Bernini and M. Canavesi, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2001, 44, 1473.
- A. Coelho, E. Sotelo, H. Novoa, O. M. Peeters, N. Biaton and E. Ravina, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, 45, 3459.
- R. Shivakumar, S. K. Gnanasam, S. Ramachandran and J. T. Leonard, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, 37, 793.
- K. M. Shubin, V. A. Kuznstsov and V. A. Galishev, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, 45, 1407.
- S. K. Kundu, A. Pramanik and A. Patra, *Syn. Lett.*, 2002, 3, 823.
- S. Demirayak, A. C. Karaburun, I. Kayagil, K. Erol and B. Sirmagul, *Archives of Pharmacol. Res.*, 2004, 27, 13.
- L. Betti, M. Floridin, G. Giannaccini, F. Manetti, G. Strappaghetti, A. Tafi and M. Botta, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2003, 13, 171.

Salvi *et al.* : Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of substituted *etc.*

11. E. Sotelo, N. Fraiz, M. Yanez, V. Terrades, R. Laguna, E. Cano and E. Ravina, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2002, 10, 2873.
12. M. Van, H. Boss, D. Couwenberg, A. Hatzelmann, G. J. Sterk, K. Goubitz, H. Schenk and H. Timmerman, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, 45, 2526.
13. M. Van, K. M. Bommele, H. Boss, A. Hatzelmann, M. Van Slingerland, G. J. Sterk and H. Timmerman, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, 46, 2008.
14. S. W. Fox, M. Fling and N. Bollenlack, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1944, 155, 465.
15. T. S. G. Jones, *Biochem. J.*, 1948, 42, 111.
16. B. J. Berger, *Antimicrob. Agent Chemo.*, 2000, 44, 2540.
17. I. O. Edafiogho, K. R. Scott, J. A. Moore and U. A. Farrar, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1991, 4, 387.
18. J. A. Ure and M. J. Perassolo, *Neurological Science*, 2000, 177, 1.
19. R. Sharma, D. P. Nagda and G. L. Talesara, *ARKIVOK*, 2006, i, 1.
20. T. Banu, S. Rajora, D. Khatri and G. L. Talesara, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, 77, 300.
21. B. Singh, D. Mehta, L. K. Baregama and G. L. Talesara, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, 43, 1306.
22. J. H. Bilman and W. F. Herlina, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1473.
23. W. R. Orndorff and D. S. Pratt, *Am. Chem. J.*, 1912, 47, 89.